

About ten stars orbit eclipsing binary XZ Andromedae

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Abstract

A third body in an eclipsing binary system causes regular periodic changes in the observed (O) minus the computed (C) eclipse epochs. Fourth bodies have rarely been detected from the O-C data. We apply the new Discrete Chi-square Method (DCM) to the O-C data of the eclipsing binary XZ Andromedae. These data contain the periodic signatures of at least ten wide orbit stars (WOSs). Their orbital periods are between 1.6 and 91.7 years. Since no changes have been observed in the eclipses of XZ And during the past 127 years, the orbits of all these WOSs are most probably co-planar. We give detailed instructions of how the professional and the amateur astronomers can easily repeat all stages of our DCM analysis with an ordinary PC, as well as apply this method to the O-C data of other eclipsing binaries.

Key words: methods: data analysis - methods: numerical - methods: statistical - binaries: eclipsing

1 Introduction

Naked eye observations of Algol’s eclipses have been recorded into the Ancient Egyptian Calendar of Lucky and Unlucky days (Jetsu and Porceddu, 2015; Jetsu et al., 2013; Porceddu et al., 2018, 2008). Today, eclipsing binary (EB) observations have become routine for the professional and the amateur astronomers. On November 29th 1890, Dr. Raymond S. Dugan recorded the first primary eclipse epoch of XZ And. The last epoch in our XZ And eclipse data is from December 24th, 2017. The primary (A4 IV-V, $3.2m_{\odot}$, $2.4R_{\odot}$) and the secondary (G IV, $1.3m_{\odot}$, $2.6R_{\odot}$) of this binary orbit each other during $P_{\text{orb}} = 1.357$ days (Demircan et al., 1995).

Periodic long-term changes are sometimes observed O-C data of EBs. A third or a fourth body can cause such periodicity (e.g. Jetsu, 2020b), but there are also other alternatives, like a magnetic activity cycle (e.g. Applegate, 1992) or an apsidal motion (e.g. Borkovits et al., 2005). Such long-term changes have also been observed in XZ And (Chaplin, 2019; Demircan et al., 1995; Manzoori, 2016). When Hajdu et al. (2019) studied O-C data of 80 000 EBs, they detected only four EB candidates that may have a fourth body. Our preliminary analysis of XZ And with the new Discrete Chi-Square Method (DCM) already confirmed the presence of a third and a fourth body (Jetsu, 2020a). Here, we show that DCM can detect the periodic O-C signals of at least ten bodies in this system. Our appendix gives detailed instructions for repeating every stage of our DCM analysis.¹

¹ DCM program code and all other necessary files are freely available in the [Zenodo database](#): doi [xx.xxxx/zenodo.xxxxxxx](#) All files, variables and other code related items are printed in [magenta](#) colour.

2 Data

In September 2019, we retrieved the observed (O) minus the computed (C) primary eclipse epochs of XZ And from the [Lichtenknecker-Database of the BAV](#). These data had been computed from the ephemeris

$$\text{HJD } 2452500.5129 + 1.35730911E. \quad (1)$$

All original O-C data are shown in Fig. 1. We reject eight secondary minima and three primary minimum outliers (Table A2). The $n = 1094$ Heliocentric Julian Day $t_i = t_{\odot,i}$ data

$$y_i = y_{\text{HJD}}(t_{\odot,i}) = O - C \quad (2)$$

are our first analysed sample (Table A3: hereafter HJD-data).

The yearly distribution of data is given in Table A4. Most of these observations have been made between August and January. The regular lack of observations between February and July is repeated in the data for 127 years. This “1^y-window” can mislead DCM period analysis. In our second analysed sample, we create random time points

$$t_i^* = t_{\odot,i} + \delta t_i \quad (3)$$

where $t_{\odot,i}$ time points are from Table A3. The random shifts δt_i are uniformly distributed between $-365.^{\text{d}}25/2$ and $+365.^{\text{d}}25/2$. These new t_i^* time points are rearranged into increasing order. No changes are made to y_i and σ_i values of Table A3. We analyse one such arbitrary sample of t_i^* , y_i and σ_i data (Table A5: hereafter D-data). We will show that the δt_i random shifts do not mislead the detection of longer periods, but they do help us in the identification of possibly spurious periods (Table A10). For example, the largest possible random shift of $\pm 183^{\text{d}}$ is only about $\pm 6\%$ for $P_{\text{min}} = 3000^{\text{d}}$, which is our lower limit for the tested longer periods of XZ And.

Figure 1: Original O-C data. Analysed data (“C” and “E” = red circles, “V” and “F” = green circles, “P” and “?” = yellow circles) and rejected data (secondary minima = transparent squares, outliers = transparent circles).

In our third sample, we transform Table A3 data to

$$y_{\text{JD}}(t_{\oplus,i}) = y_{\text{HJD}}(t_{\odot,i}) - \delta t_i, \quad (4)$$

where $\delta t_i = t_{\odot,i} - t_{\oplus,i}$, and t_{\odot} and $t_{\oplus,i}$ are the epochs when the same eclipse of XZ And is observed in the Sun and on the Earth (Table A6: hereafter JD-data). No changes are made to t_i and σ_i values of Table A3. We use XZ And coordinates $\alpha = 01^{\text{h}} 53^{\text{m}} 48.^{\text{s}}76$ and $\delta = +41^{\circ} 51' 24.97''$ in the transformation of Eq. 4. This transformation superimposes the artificial “1 ν -signal”, the Earth’s motion around the Sun, into these data. We use this 1 ν -signal for checking the reliability of our period analysis. For XZ And, this effect is about ± 7.4 minutes = ± 0.0051 days.

Since the errors σ of the data are unknown, we use the following arbitrary relative weights for different observations

$$w_1 = 3 \text{ for “C” } (n = 55) \text{ and “E” } (n = 29)$$

$$w_2 = 2 \text{ for “V” } (n = 939) \text{ and “F” } (n = 61)$$

$$w_3 = 1 \text{ for “P” } (n = 7) \text{ and “?” } (n = 3),$$

where the BAV observation systems in German language are “C = CCD”, “E = Fotometer”, “V = Visuel”, “F = Fotoserie”, “P = Platten” and “? = Unbekant”. First, we fix the errors for the most accurate “C” and “E” observations to $\sigma_1 = 0.^{\text{d}}001$. Then, the $w = \sigma^{-2}$ relation gives the errors $\sigma_2 = \sqrt{2\sigma_1^2/3} = 0.^{\text{d}}00122$ for the “V” and “F” observations,

as well as $\sigma_3 = \sqrt{2\sigma_1^2/3} = 0.^{\text{d}}00173$ for the “P” and “?” observations. The numerical values of these errors do not influence our results, because we use the same weight for every observation. These errors are used only to give the correct DCM code analysis format for our three files of data.

3 Method

The data are $y_i = y(t_i) \pm \sigma_i$, where t_i are the observing times and σ_i are the errors ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$). The time span is $\Delta T = t_n - t_1$. We apply DCM to these data. This method can detect many signals superimposed on arbitrary trends. Detailed instructions for using the DCM python code were already given in Jetsu (2020a, Appendix). Here, we also provide all necessary information for reproducing our DCM analysis of XZ And data.

DCM model is a sum of a periodic function $h(t)$ and an aperiodic function $p(t)$

$$g(t) = g(t, K_1, K_2, K_3) = h(t) + p(t), \quad (5)$$

where

$$h(t) = h(t, K_1, K_2) = \sum_{i=1}^{K_1} h_i(t) \quad (6)$$

$$h_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{K_2} B_{i,j} \cos(2\pi j f_i t) + C_{i,j} \sin(2\pi j f_i t) \quad (7)$$

$$p(t) = p(t, K_3) = \sum_{k=0}^{K_3} p_k(t) \quad (8)$$

$$p_k(t) = M_k \left[\frac{2t}{\Delta T} \right]^k. \quad (9)$$

The periodic $h(t)$ function is a sum of K_1 harmonic f_i frequency signals $h_i(t)$. The order of these signals is K_2 . The trend $p(t)$ is an aperiodic K_3 order polynomial. The $g(t)$ model has

$$p = K_1 \times (2K_2 + 1) + K_3 + 1 \quad (10)$$

free parameters. We use the abbreviation “model $_{K_1, K_2, K_3}$ ” for a model having orders K_1 , K_2 and K_3 . DCM determines the $h_i(t)$ signal parameters

$$P_i = 1/f_i = \text{Period}$$

$$A_i = \text{Peak to peak amplitude}$$

$$t_{i, \min, 1} = \text{Deeper primary minimum epoch}$$

$$t_{i, \min, 2} = \text{Secondary minimum epoch (if present)}$$

$$t_{i, \max, 1} = \text{Higher primary maximum epoch}$$

$$t_{i, \max, 2} = \text{Secondary maximum epoch (if present),}$$

and the M_k parameters of the $p(t)$ trend.

We compute the DCM test statistic z from the sum of squared residuals R , because the errors for the data are unknown (Jetsu, 2020a, Eqs. 9 and 11). The $F = F_R$ test statistic gives the Fisher-test critical levels Q_F (Jetsu, 2020a, Eqs. 13). When we compare a simple and a complex model, the latter is a better model for the data if

$$Q_F < \gamma_F = 0.001, \quad (11)$$

where $\gamma_F = 0.001$ is the pre-assigned significance level (Jetsu, 2020a, Eq. 14).

Our notations for the two signatures of unstable models are

* = Dispersing amplitudes

† = Intersecting frequencies

The former can occur without the latter, but not vice versa (Jetsu, 2020a, Sect. 4.3.). The periods that are clearly too large are also denoted with †. We use the notation

• = Failed model

when * and † both occur, or the model must be rejected with the criterion of Eq. 11.

4 Search for long periods

We first search for longer periods between $P_{\min} = 3000^d$ and $P_{\max} = 100\,000^d$, because the 1^y -window and 1^y -signal can mislead the detection of periods below P_{\min} . Later, we will also search for periods shorter than P_{\min} (Sect. 5). Note that $P_{\max} > \Delta T = 46\,111^d$, because we will show that DCM can detect periods longer than the time span of data. We search for periodicity in three different samples, where the misleading 1^y -window or 1^y -signal is present or absent. These are

HJD-data: 1^y -window = Yes, 1^y -signal = No

D-data: 1^y -window = No, 1^y -signal = No

JD-data: 1^y -window = Yes, 1^y -signal = Yes

We analyse the original HJD-data first, because the 1^y -signal does not contaminate these data. The one signal model periods $P_1 = 58237^d$ and 13148^d are different (Table A7: Models M=1 and 2). Fisher-test reveals that the latter quadratic $K_3 = 2$ trend model $_{1,1,2}$ is certainly a better model for the data than the linear $K_3 = 1$ trend model $_{1,1,1}$ (Table A7: M=1, †, $F = 149$, $Q_F < 10^{-16}$). Both two signal models M=3 and 4 give the period $P_1 \approx 13300^d$, but the P_2 periods of these models are different. Also for these two signal models, the $K_3 = 2$ quadratic trend model $_{2,1,2}$ is better than the linear $K_3 = 1$ trend model $_{2,1,1}$ (Table A7: M=3, †, $F = 390$, $Q_F < 10^{-16}$). The same $\sim 13300^d$ period is also present in the three signal model $_{3,1,1}$ and model $_{3,1,2}$, but the other two periods of these models differ (Table A7: M=5 and 6). Model M=5 fails (•), because the two largest periods have dispersing amplitudes (*) and the largest one is unrealistic (†). This linear trend three signal model M=5 has $p = 11$ free parameters. Yet, the simple quadratic trend two signal model M=4, having only $p = 8$ free parameters, is certainly a better model for the data (Table A7: M=4, †, $F = 0$, $Q_F = 1.0$). This is very strong evidence for the $K_3 = 2$ quadratic $p(t)$ trend in these data. The linear trend four signal model M=7 fails (•). All † arrows point towards model M=8 in the second last column of Table A7. This four signal model $_{4,1,2}$ is certainly the best one of all eight compared models, because it beats the other seven models by an absolute certainty of $Q_F < 10^{-16}$. The periodograms for this model $_{4,1,2}$, and the model itself, are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The transparent diamonds denoting the red z_1 and the blue z_2 periodogram minima for the two weaker periodicities are certainly real. When all four periodograms are plotted in the same scale, these two minima appear to be shallow only because the two larger amplitude periodic signals clearly dominate in this model M=8. These two high amplitude signals have a much bigger impact on the squared sum of residuals R than the two low amplitude signals. When the tested frequencies approach zero, the yellow z_4 periodogram turns upwards in the lower panel of Fig. 2. Thus, DCM can confirm that none of the periods longer than ΔT fit to these data. The level of residuals is stable, but some regular patterns indicate that there are more than four signals in these data (Fig. 3: blue dots). Each $h_j(t_i)$ signal

$$y_{i,j} = y_i - [g(t_i) - h_j(t_i)] \quad (12)$$

is also shown in Fig. 4. The main results in Table A7 are

- R1. These data contain a quadratic $p(t)$ trend $K_3 = 2$.
- R2. The periods and amplitudes of all quadratic trend $K_3 = 2$ models are consistent (Table A7: M=2, 4, 6 and 8)). When we detect a new signal, we re-detect exactly the same old signal periods and signal amplitudes.
- R3. There are at least four signals, because model $_{4,1,2}$ beats the other models with an absolute certainty of $Q_F < 10^{-16}$.

Figure 2: Periodograms for four signal model_{4,1,2} of Table A7 (M=8). Colours are red (z_1), blue (z_2), green (z_3) and yellow (z_4) (Jetsu, 2020a, Eq. 17). Open diamonds denote best frequencies.

Figure 3: Data and model M=8 of Table A7. (a) Data (black dots) and $p(t)$ trend (dotted black line). (b) Data minus $p(t)$ trend (black dots), $g(t)$ minus $p(t)$ (black line), $g_1(t)$ signal (red line), $g_2(t)$ signal (blue line), $g_3(t)$ signal (green line) and $g_4(t)$ signal (yellow line). Residuals (blue dots) are offset to -0.012 (dotted blue line).

Figure 4: Four signals in original data. Signals $y_{i,j}$ (Eq. 12) for model M=8 of Table A7. Each signal is plotted as a function of time (t) and phase (ϕ).

Figure 5: Four signal residuals (Table A9: M=8), otherwise as in Fig. 3.

Figure 6: Four signals in four signal residuals. Signals $y_{i,j}$ (Eq. 12) for model M=8 in Table A9, otherwise as in Fig. 4.

Figure 7: Failed three signal model for original data (Table A9: M=5), otherwise as in Fig. 3.

Figure 8: Failed model for original data. Signals $y_{i,j}$ (Eq. 12) for model M=5 in Table A7. Otherwise as in Fig. 4.

Figure 9: 1^y -signal in JD-data. Signal $y_{i,j}$ (Eq. 12) for model M=9 in Table A15, otherwise as in Fig. 9.

We use the above R1, R2 and R3 abbreviations for these particular results. The quadratic $K_3 = 2$ trend is hereafter used in all models for the original data (R1 result).

It takes several days for an ordinary PC to compute the four signal model_{4,1,2} and its 20 bootstrap rounds (Figs. 2, 3 and 4). The five signal model computation would take months. We solve this problem with Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³ and Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴ approach. First, the original data are analysed with the quadratic trend model. Then, we analyse the three or four signal residuals with the constant trend model (e.g. Fig. 5). This gives us the six or eight signal residuals, which are analysed with the constant trend model. We end this process at 3+3+3+3 or 4+4+4 = 12 signals. The results for our three samples are given in Tables A8 and A9 (HJD-data), Tables A10 and A11 (D-data), and Tables A12 and A13 (JD-data). All these results are compared in Table A14.

Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³ results for HJD-data, D-data and JD-data agree in Table A14. The same applies to Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴ results. In all the above mentioned tables, we use the symbol

\mathfrak{N}^9 = Weakest of first nine detected signals

to denote the periodicity that has the lowest amplitude of all nine first detected signals. We choose these \mathfrak{N}^9 periods from models M=9 (Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³) and M=12 (Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴). If these \mathfrak{N}^9 periods were ignored in Table A14, the results would be the same for the eight best Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³ and Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴ periods. The main results in Table A14 are

R4 These data contain at least seven or eight signals.

R5 Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³ and Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴ give the same results for the eight best periods in all three samples.

R6 There is no 1^y -window and no 1^y -signal bias, because all three samples give the same results.

We use the words “at least” in R4 result, because HJD-data or D-data may contain even more periodicities. For example, Fisher-test does not require the rejection of the ninth signal in HJD-data (Tables A8 and A9: M=9). Another uncertainty is connected to the failed (\bullet) model M=6 in Tables A8, A9, A10 and A11. The two periods above and below 4500^d show amplitude dispersion ($*$) and intersecting frequencies (\dagger). DCM does not tend to find too many signals, but it may find too few (see Jetsu, 2020a, Sect. 4.4). However, we can not confirm, if these two periods above and below 4500^d represent two separate signals.

The results for the four signal residuals are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. These two figures “speak for themselves”, because the scatter of the new more accurate data is extremely small. It seems as if these black dots of new data were glued on the $h_i(t)$ curves. The scatter definitely increases for the older less accurate data. The eight signal residuals (blue dots) still show some regularity, but only for the more accurate new data. One failed model is also shown in Figs. 7 and 8. Note that the solution for $p(t)$ (black dotted line) makes no sense, and nor does the solution for $h_3(t)$ (green continuous line).

5 Search for short periods

The eight best Test^{4+4+4} periods are the same for HJD-data, D-data and JD-data (R5 result). Therefore, we search for shorter periods in the residuals of the eight signal models $M=8$ of these three samples. The tested DCM period range is between $P_{\min} = 300^{\text{d}}$ and $P_{\max} = 3000^{\text{d}}$. Shorter P_{\min} values would only lead to the “detection” of spurious signals, like $1/2$, $2/3$, $3/4 \times 1^{\text{y}}$ -window or 1^{y} -signal. The short period search results are given in Table A15.

The first period $P_1 = 365.^{\text{d}}6 \pm 78^{\text{d}}$ in HJD-data comes from the 1^{y} -signal period, although this signal should have been removed from these Heliocentric Julian Days. While the 1^{y} -window may cause this periodicity, it may also be present, because the units of some epochs are Julian Days, i.e. the δt_i correction of Eq. 4 has not been applied. The amplitude $A_2 = 0.^{\text{d}}0013$ of the latter second $P_2 = 616.^{\text{d}}6$ signal is approximately equal to the amplitudes of weakest nine first detected long period signals (\mathfrak{N}^9) in Table A14. Hence, this second signal may represent a real periodicity. The third or the fourth short periodicity alternatives fail (Table A15: $M=3$ and 4 have “•”).

Fisher-test indicates that there may be even three short period signals in the eight signal residuals of D-data (Table A15: models $M=5-7$). The first one, $P_1 = 364.^{\text{d}}9 \pm 33^{\text{d}}$, is again the 1^{y} -signal. This time the 1^{y} -window can not explain this periodicity, because this window is removed from D-data (Eq. 3). The only realistic cause for this periodicity is the wrong Julian Day units of some epochs. There can not be only a few such wrong epochs, because the δt_i random shifts of Eq. 3 would otherwise eliminate this 1^{y} -signal. The second $P_2 = 593.^{\text{d}}1 \pm 26^{\text{d}}$ period is equal to the P_2 period already detected from HJD-data. It also has the same amplitude $A_2 = 0.^{\text{d}}0013$. The third $P_3 = 2244^{\text{d}} \pm 19^{\text{d}}$ signal is even stronger, $A_3 = 0.^{\text{d}}0016$. There is no fourth signal, because model $M=8$ fails (•).

Only one period dominates the eight signal residuals of JD-data: 1^{y} -signal (Table A15: other models $M=10-12$ have “•”). This regular artificial signal is shown in Fig. 9. DCM detects an extremely accurate value for this period, $P_1 = 365.^{\text{d}}34 \pm 0.^{\text{d}}08$. The amplitude $A_1 = 0.^{\text{d}}0110 \pm 0.^{\text{d}}0004$ of this 1^{y} -signal agrees perfectly with the expected superimposed signal amplitude value $\pm 0.^{\text{d}}0051 \equiv 0.^{\text{d}}0102$ (Eq. 4). Our unambiguous re-detection of this superimposed 1^{y} -signal is possible *only if* all earlier eight long period signals detected from JD-data are also real. Even a single wrong long period $h_i(t)$ signal could weaken or erase this 1^{y} -signal, let alone many wrong long period $h_i(t)$ signals or a wrong $p(t)$ trend. The unexpected 1^{y} -signal signatures in HJD-data and D-data also support this same detection of eight real long periods, because some epochs probably have the wrong units, Julian Days. The main results in Table A15 are

- R7. The unambiguous detection of the artificially superimposed 1^{y} -signal in JD-data strongly supports the idea that the eight detected long periods of XZ And are real.
- R8. Signatures of $\sim 600^{\text{d}}$ signal are detected in all three samples. D-data 2244^{d} signal may also be a real periodicity.

6 Discussion

6.1 Period analysis

While it is not possible to determine the *exact* number of stars in XZ And, there are definitely many. For example, the current O-C data can not confirm if the two signals below and above 4500^{d} represent one or two periodicities/stars (e.g. Table A8: $M=6$). Another example is the short 2244^{d} period detected in D-data, which is not detected in HJD-data or JD-data (Table A15: $M=7$). This detection could be explained with 1^{y} -window, which has been removed only from the D-data. There are also Fisher-test cases that resemble the children’s game stone-paper-scissors, where stone wins scissors, paper wins stone, and scissors win paper (e.g. Table A15: models $M=1-4$ and $M=9-12$). The results for these tests also depend on the chosen pre-assigned critical level γ_F in the criterion of Eq. 11. In all long period searches, the Q_F critical levels are extremely significant for seven, eight or even nine first detected signals. Then this significance drops abruptly for the next signals. Exactly the same results were obtained for simulated data by Jetsu (2020a, their Table 4). DCM may find too few signals, especially if the $p(t)$ trend is wrong. However, DCM tends not to detect too many signals, because such models fail (•).

DCM analysis does not require access to super computers. The results for $\text{Test}^{3+3+3+3}$ and Test^{4+4+4} confirm that the computation capacity of small PCs is sufficient for detecting many signals in the O-C data of EBs. The computations for the bootstrap error estimates of three and four signal models take a long time. The best alternative is to run only a few bootstrap rounds first, and test many bootstrap rounds only if the preliminary analysis results make sense. Note that the bootstrap never gives exactly the same error estimates because it uses random samples of residuals.

We do not re-discuss our main results R1 - R8. The fact that DCM re-detects the artificial 1^{y} -signal in JD-data proves beyond any reasonable doubt that the other detected signals represent real periodicities. We succeed in this *after* removing a quadratic $p(t)$ trend and eight $h_i(t)$ signals.

The model used by Hajdu et al. (2019, their Eq. 11) was the sum of a parabola and a sinusoid. Their detection rate of fourth bodies in EBs was only 0.00005. Jetsu (2019) has already shown that the one-dimensional period finding methods, like the power spectrum method (Lomb, 1976; Scargle, 1982; Zechmeister and Kürster, 2009), give spurious results if the data contains many signals. This applies also to the one-dimensional periodic model applied by Hajdu et al. (2019), and explains their low detection rate of fourth bodies. At the same time, their low detection rate merely highlights the potential of DCM.

Jetsu (2020a, Sect. 6.) already discussed the problems arising from the use of $K_2 = 2$ double wave models. All third bodies do not necessarily induce sinusoidal O-C changes. Therefore, the temptation for using $K_2 = 2$ harmonics arises. This approach opens up a real Pandora’s box, because two stars having periods P_1 and P_2 induce a synodic period $(P_1^{-1} - P_2^{-1})^{-1}$. These synodic periods are repeated through

Table 1: Masses m_3 from p_3 and a of Eq. 13. Eight periods are from long search (Long) and two periods from short search (Short). We refer to these stars as S_1, \dots, S_{10} . Masses are computed for $i = 90^\circ, 60^\circ$ and 30° ($m_3^{i=90}, m_3^{i=60}, m_3^{i=30}$).

Search	Star	p_3		a	$m_3^{i=90}$	$m_3^{i=60}$	$m_3^{i=30}$
		[d]	[y]				
Long	S_1	33507	91.7	0.04300	1.16	1.38	2.74
Long	S_2	13537	37.1	0.02840	1.45	1.73	3.56
Long	S_3	7754	21.2	0.00310	0.20	0.23	0.40
Long	S_4	6346	17.4	0.00275	0.20	0.23	0.41
Long	S_5	4723	12.9	0.00200	0.18	0.20	0.36
Long	S_6	4320	11.8	0.00250	0.24	0.27	0.49
Long	S_7	3732	10.2	0.00130	0.13	0.15	0.27
Long	S_8	3019	8.3	0.00120	0.14	0.16	0.29
Short	S_9	2244	6.1	0.00080	0.11	0.13	0.23
Short	S_{10}	592	1.6	0.00060	0.21	0.25	0.44

out the whole data, and DCM certainly detects them. If we had used the $K_2 = 2$ option in our analysis, the interactions between the signals of all stars in XZ And would have caused an incredible mess.

6.2 Astrophysics

Activity cycles are quasi-periodic, and never give regular long-term residuals. Therefore, the Applegate (1992) mechanism can not explain the numerous O-C periods of XZ And. An apsidal motion can cause only one period. If the light-time effect (LTE) of a third body causes these periodic O-C changes, the mass function fulfills

$$f(m_3) = \frac{(m_3 \sin i)^3}{[m_1(1+q) + m_3]^2} = \frac{(713.15 a)^3}{p_3^2}, \quad (13)$$

where i is the inclination of the orbital plane of the third body, m_1 is the mass of primary [m_\odot], $q = m_2/m_1$ is the dimensionless mass ratio of secondary and primary, m_3 is the mass of the third body [m_\odot], $a = A/2$ is half of the peak the peak amplitude of O-C modulation caused by the third body [d], and p_3 is the period of the modulations caused by the third body [y] (Borkovits and Hegedues, 1996; Tanriver, 2015; Yang et al., 2016). We use the masses $m_1 = 3.2m_\odot$ and $m_2 = 1.3m_\odot$ (Demircan et al., 1995, A4 IV + G5 IV). The long period search p and a values are those detected from HJD-data (Table A9: M=4 and 8). The respective two short period values are detected from HJD-data and D-data (Table A15: M=4 and 7). We compute the m_3 values for inclinations $i = 90^\circ, 60^\circ$ and 30° (Table 1). In the $i = 90^\circ$ alternative, the mass $1.45m_\odot$ of star S_2 exceeds the $m_2 = 1.3m_\odot$ mass of the secondary. The $1.16m_\odot$ mass of S_1 star is just below this limit. If the remaining eight less massive stars were in the main sequence, they would all belong to spectral type M. The $m_1 = 3.2m_\odot$ primary would dominate the luminosity of such a system of twelve stars. If the inclination were $i = 60^\circ$, the S_1 and S_2 star masses would exceed the secondary m_2 mass,

Table 2: Some earlier O - C cycle detections.

[y]	[d]	Reference
137.5	50222	Demircan et al. (1995)
36.8	13441	Demircan et al. (1995)
11.2	4091	Demircan et al. (1995)
34.8	12711	Manzoori (2016)
23.3	8510	Manzoori (2016)
38	13879	Chaplin (2019)

but the m_1 primary would still dominate the luminosity of the whole system. The $i = 30^\circ$ alternative can be ruled out, because the S_2 star would be more massive and brighter than the primary, and this practically constant short-term radial velocity star would have been noticed long ago. The orbital period 37.71 of this S_2 star has also been detected in several previous studies (Table 2).

The quadratic polynomial trend is

$$p(t) = M_0 + M_1 c t + M_2 c^2 t^2,$$

where $c = 2/\Delta T$. The time derivative is

$$\frac{dp(t)}{dt} = M_1 c + 2M_2 c^2 t.$$

We use the values $M_1 = -0.627 \pm 0.005$ and $M_2 = 0.082 \pm 0.002$ of the four signal model for the original HJD-data (Table A16: M=4). The $p(t)$ changes caused by parameter $M_1 c$ can be eliminated by computing the O-C values with a new constant period $P' = P - (M_1 c)/P = 1.^d3573458$. Hence, the only real period change is $\Delta P = 2M_2 c^2 = 4.^d1 \times 10^{-10} = 3.^s6 \times 10^{-5}$ during $P = 1.^d335730911$. The period increases because $M_2 > 0$. The long-term increase rate is

$$\frac{\Delta P}{P} = 2M_2 c^2 = (3.04 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-10}, \quad (14)$$

which is about five times less than the $\Delta P/P = 1.45 \times 10^{-9}$ estimate of XZ And obtained by Manzoori (2016). The two and the three signal model results would have been nearly the same, but the one signal model M_1 and M_2 values would have given a completely wrong result (Table A16). We do not derive any mass transfer estimate for XZ And (e.g. Manzoori, 2016, their Eq. 8). This estimate would not be correct for a multiple star system, where the numerous WOSs can perturb the central EB, e.g. through the Kozai effect (Kozai, 1962), or the combination of Kozai cycle and tidal friction effects (Fabrycky and Tremaine, 2007).

Our solar system is stable because the orbital planes of planets are nearly co-planar, the biggest exception being the smallest planet Mercury with an inclination of seven degrees. The single stars, the multiple star systems and the planets form in co-planar protostellar disks (e.g. Watkins et al., 1998). If the orbital plane of a third body is not co-planar with, or perpendicular to, the orbital plane of the central EB, periodic long-term perturbations change the orbital plane of the central EB, and the eclipses may no longer occur (Soderhjelm,

1975, Eq. 27). Since no such effects have been observed in XZ And in over a century, the planes of *all* WOSs are most probably co-planar. There orbital plane of central EB is stable for $\Psi = 0^\circ$ or 90° , where Ψ is the angle between central EB orbital plane and WOSs orbital plane. This is the case for Algol (Baron et al., 2012, Algol AB and Algol C have $\Psi = 90.^\circ20 \pm 0.^\circ32$), where two new wide orbit stars Algol D and Algol E were recently detected by Jetsu (2020b).

7 Conclusions

Hajdu et al. (2019) detected only four candidates possibly having a fourth body in their O-C data of 80 000 eclipsing binaries. The probability for detecting a fourth body from their O-C data was only 0.00005. Here, we apply the new Discrete Chi-Square Method (DCM) to the O-C data of the eclipsing binary XZ And, and detect signatures of at least ten wide orbit stars (WOSs) orbiting the central EB. These WOSs have orbital periods between $1.^\circ6$ and $91.^\circ7$. Two WOSs are certainly more massive than the Sun. The orbits of *all* these WOSs are most probably co-planar with, or perpendicular to, the orbital plane of central EB, because no changes have been observed in the eclipses of XZ And in over a century. Considering the number of new companions detected in XZ And, it is actually a more interesting multiple star system than Algol itself (Jetsu, 2020b, “only” two new companions Algol D and Algol E). Our results for XZ And and Algol confirm that many EBs have unknown companions, which can be easily detected with our DCM. This abstract mathematical method is not designed for analysing any particular phenomena of the real physical world. The O-C data of EBs just happen to be one particular type of suitable data. We sincerely hope that these results would ignite a “renaissance” in the O-C data studies of other EBs. Valuable data have been patiently collected by the professional and the amateur astronomers since the well-known amateur astronomer Sir John Goodricke re-detected Algol’s periodic eclipses (Goodricke, 1783).

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A Reproducing our results

In this appendix, we give all necessary information for reproducing the results of our DCM period analysis. DCM manual [manual.pdf](#), and all other required analysis files, can be copied from the Zenodo database. Copy the analysis files to the same folder in your computer. Do not edit these analysis files.

The DCM analysis program file is

`dcm.py`

The three different `file1` data files are

`hjdXZAnd.dat` = HJD-data = Table A3

`dXZAnd.dat` = D-data = Table A5

`jdXZAnd.dat` = JD-data = Table A6

There are 98 control files, which are specified in the last columns of Tables A8, A9, A10, A11, A12, A13 and A15. All our results can be reproduced by using these control files. For example, the two linux commands

Table A1: `dcm.dat` control file name notations.

	Meaning	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
<code>hjd</code>	HJD-data	<code>hjd</code>	*	*	*	*
<code>jd</code>	D-data	<code>jd</code>	*	*	*	*
<code>jd</code>	JD-data	<code>jd</code>	*	*	*	*
<code>14</code>	Signals 1-4 for data	*	<code>14</code>	*	*	*
<code>58</code>	Signals 5-8 for residuals	*	<code>58</code>	*	*	*
<code>912</code>	Signals 9-12 for residuals	*	<code>912</code>	*	*	*
<code>13</code>	Signals 1-3 for data	*	<code>13</code>	*	*	*
<code>46</code>	Signals 4-6 for residuals	*	<code>46</code>	*	*	*
<code>79</code>	Signals 7-9 for residuals	*	<code>79</code>	*	*	*
<code>1012</code>	Signals 10-12 for residuals	*	<code>1012</code>	*	*	*
<code>R</code>	<i>R</i> test statistic	*	*	<code>R</code>	*	*
<code>111</code>	model _{1,1,1} for data	*	*	*	<code>111</code>	*
<code>112</code>	model _{1,1,2} for data	*	*	*	<code>112</code>	*
<code>211</code>	model _{2,1,1} for data	*	*	*	<code>211</code>	*
<code>212</code>	model _{2,1,2} for data	*	*	*	<code>212</code>	*
<code>311</code>	model _{3,1,1} for data	*	*	*	<code>311</code>	*
<code>312</code>	model _{3,1,2} for data	*	*	*	<code>312</code>	*
<code>411</code>	model _{4,1,1} for data	*	*	*	<code>411</code>	*
<code>412</code>	model _{4,1,2} for data	*	*	*	<code>412</code>	*
<code>110</code>	model _{1,1,0} for residuals	*	*	*	<code>110</code>	*
<code>210</code>	model _{2,1,0} for residuals	*	*	*	<code>210</code>	*
<code>310</code>	model _{3,1,0} for residuals	*	*	*	<code>310</code>	*
<code>410</code>	model _{4,1,0} for residuals	*	*	*	<code>410</code>	*
<code>s</code>	Small frequencies	*	*	*	*	<code>s</code>
<code>l</code>	Large frequencies	*	*	*	*	<code>l</code>

`cp hjd14R111s.dat dcm.dat`

`python dcm.py`

reproduce model_{1,1,1} period analysis results given in the first line of Table A7 (M=1). In other words, the control file `dcm.dat` is an exact copy of `hjd14R111s.dat`. This control file specifies what kind of a DCM analysis the program `dcm.py` should perform. The meaning of all control file `dcm.dat` parameters is explained in the manual [manual.pdf](#).

The naming conventions of our control files are given in Table A1. These names are formed by using a sequence N1 + N2 + N3 + N4 + N5. The first N1 notation `hjd` in the file name `hjd14R111s.dat` means that we analyse HJD-data. The N2 notation `14` means that we search for the four first signals in the original data. The N3 notation `R` indicates that the DCM test statistic *z* is computed from the sum of squared residuals *R* (Jetsu, 2020a, Eqs. 9 and 11). The N4 notation `111` tells that we use model_{1,1,1}. The last N5 notation `s` refers to the search for small frequencies (long period search between 3000 and 100 000 days). All figures and files produced by `dcm.py` begin with the tag `hjd14R111s`, e.g. the periodogram figure `hjd14R111sz.eps` or the result file `hjd14R111sParams.dat`.

DCM analysis program `dcm.py` can be applied to the O-C data of any other star, if the format for the data file `file1` and the control file `dcm.dat` are the same as in this paper.

Table A2: Rejected data. Date, UT and rejection criterion

Date	UT	Criterion
06.10.1923	21:36	Secondary minimum
11.11.1949	05:47	Secondary minimum
17.09.1965	01:13	Secondary minimum
25.11.1975	17:56	Secondary minimum
26.12.1996	00:04	Secondary minimum
03.01.2008	18:51	Secondary minimum
21.12.2009	19:03	Secondary minimum
14.08.2010	23:02	Secondary minimum
18.09.1923	17:02	Outlier
01.10.1923	18:57	Outlier
02.12.1923	19:00	Outlier

Table A3: O-C data in file `hjdXZAnd.dat`. Columns are primary eclipse epoch in the Sun (t_{\odot}) and observed minus computed eclipse epoch of Eq. 2 ($y_{\text{HJD}} \pm \sigma_{y_{\text{HJD}}}$). Only three first values of all $n = 1091$ values are shown.

t_{\odot} [HJD]	y_{HJD} [d]	$\sigma_{y_{\text{HJD}}}$ [d]
2411700.59000	0.789000	0.000173
2412080.62900	0.781000	0.000173
2412711.78000	0.784000	0.000173
...

Table A4: Yearly distribution of data

Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
98	62	25	5	4	11	56	142	220	197	153	121

Table A5: O-C data in file `dxZAnd.dat`. Time points computed from Eq. 3, otherwise as in Table A3.

2411655.32320	0.789000	0.000173
2411965.26421	0.781000	0.000173
2412702.44481	0.784000	0.000173
...

Table A6: O-C data in file `jdXZAnd.dat`. Columns are primary eclipse epoch on the Earth (t_{\oplus}) and observed minus computed eclipse epoch of Eq. 4 ($y_{\text{JD}} \pm \sigma_{y_{\text{JD}}}$), otherwise as in Table A3.

t_{\oplus} [JD]	y_{JD} [d]	$\sigma_{y_{\text{JD}}}$ [d]
2411700.590000	0.793510	0.000173
2412080.629000	0.784770	0.000173
2412711.780000	0.786750	0.000173
...

Table A7: Long period search between 3000^d and 100000^d for HJD-data. Col 1. Model number M. Col 2. model_{K₁,K₂,K₃}, p = number of free parameters and R = sum of squared residuals. Cols 3-6. Period analysis results: Detected periods P_1, \dots, P_4 and amplitudes A_1, \dots, A_4 . Cols 7-13. Fisher test results: “ \uparrow ” \equiv complex model above is better than left side simple model, “ \leftarrow ” \equiv left side simple model is better than complex model above, F = Fisher test statistic and Q_F = critical level. Col 14. Figure numbers and control file **dcm.dat**. Notations “*”, “ \dagger ” and “ \bullet ” are explained in Sect. 3.

1.	2.	3.				4.				5.				14.
		Period analysis				Original data (Table A3 = file1 = hjdXZAnd.dat)				Fisher-test				
M	Model	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{1,1,2}	model _{2,1,1}	model _{2,1,2}	model _{3,1,1}	model _{3,1,2}	model _{4,1,1}	model _{4,1,2}		
1	model _{1,1,1} $p=5$ $R=0.4089$	58237±2998 0.24±0.02	-	-	-	\uparrow $F=149$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=4260$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=4436$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2952$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2855$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2222$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2296$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd14R111s.dat	
2	model _{1,1,2} $p=6$ $R=0.3595$	13148±109 0.050±0.001	-	-	-	-	\uparrow $F=5552$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=5157$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=3088$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2907$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2182$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2228$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd14R112s.dat	
3	model _{2,1,1} $p=8$ $R=0.03200$	13252±34 0.0556±0.0006	42430±319 0.146±0.002	-	-	-	-	\uparrow $F=390$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=130$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=142$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=95.1$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=115$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd14R211s.dat	
4	model _{2,1,2} $p=9$ $R=0.02354$	13420±29 0.0582±0.0003	32196 ± 259 0.081±0.001	-	-	-	-	-	\leftarrow $F=0$ $Q_F = 1.0$	\uparrow $F=44.0$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=26.9$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=50.9$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd14R212s.dat	
5	model _{3,1,1} $p=11$ $R=0.02354$	13421±23 0.0582±0.0005	31775±1724 0.08±0.01*	173497±302046 0.6±0.2* \dagger	-	-	-	-	-	\uparrow $F=132$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=44.8$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=76.4$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd14R311s.dat Figs. 7 and 8	
6	model _{3,1,2} $p=12$ $R=0.02098$	8124±139 0.0044±0.0004	13439±25 0.0575±0.0004	32948±340 0.084±0.001	-	-	-	-	-	-	\leftarrow $F=1.3$ $Q_F=0.28$	\uparrow $F=51.7$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd14R312s.dat	
7	model _{4,1,1} $p=14$ $R=0.02093$	8264±126 0.0046±0.0004	13393±11 0.0574±0.0004	30644±1689 0.07±0.01*	333333±1535441 5261±2447* \dagger	-	-	-	-	-	-	\uparrow $F=114$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd14R412s.dat	
8	model _{4,1,2} $p=15$ $R=0.01834$	6346±63 0.0055±0.0004	7754±67 0.0062±0.0005	13537±28 0.0568±0.0002	33507±246 0.086±0.001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	dcm.dat = hjd14R412s.dat Figs. 2 , 3 and 4	

Table A8: Long period search between 3000^d and 100000^d. Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³ for HJD-data. Notation “ $\mathbb{9}$ ” is explained in Sect 4, otherwise as in Table A7.

M	Model	Original data (Table A3 = file1 = hjdXZAnd.dat)			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,2}	model _{3,1,2}	
1	model _{1,1,2} $p=6$ $R=0.3595$	13148±92 0.050±0.002	-	-	\uparrow $F=5157$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	\uparrow $F=2907$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd13R112s.dat
2	model _{2,1,2} $p=9$ $R=0.02354$	13420±21 0.0582±0.0005	32196±335 0.081±0.002	-	-	\uparrow $F=44.0$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd13R212s.dat
3	model _{3,1,2} $p=12$ $R=0.02098$	8124±127 0.0044±0.0004	13439±23 0.0575±0.0004	32948±273 0.084±0.001	-	-	dcm.dat = hjd13R312s.dat
Residuals of three signals (file1 = hjd13R312sResiduals.dat)							
M	Model	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	Fisher-test		
4	model _{1,1,0} $p=4$ $R=0.01898$	6078±70 0.0038±0.0004	-	-	\uparrow $F=17.8$ $Q_F = 2.7 \times 10^{-11}$	\uparrow $F=20.2$ $Q_F < 10^{-16}$	dcm.dat = hjd46R110s.dat
5	model _{2,1,0} $p=7$ $R=0.01809$	2960±25 0.0026±0.0004	6061±52 0.0040±0.0003	-	-	\uparrow $F=21.6$ $Q_F = 1.4 \times 10^{-13}$	dcm.dat = hjd46R210s.dat
6	model _{3,1,0} $p=10$ $R=0.01707$	4480±91 0.01±0.02* \dagger	4614±80 0.01±0.02* \dagger	6092±379 0.0044±0.0004	-	-	dcm.dat = hjd46R310s.dat
Residuals of six signals (file1 = hjd46R310sResiduals.dat)							
M	Model	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	Fisher-test		
7	model _{1,1,0} $p=4$ $R=0.01633$	2988±22 0.0024±0.0004	-	-	\uparrow $F=15.0$ $Q_F = 1.4 \times 10^{-9}$	\uparrow $F=11.3$ $Q_F = 3.0 \times 10^{-12}$	dcm.dat = hjd79R110s.dat
8	model _{2,1,0} $p=7$ $R=0.01568$	3005±26 0.0025±0.0003	3686±32 0.0022±0.0003	-	-	\uparrow $F=7.3$ $Q_F = 0.000078$	dcm.dat = hjd79R210s.dat
9	model _{3,1,0} $p=10$ $R=0.01537$	3006±18 0.0026±0.0004	3687±34 0.0022±0.0003	7518±219 $\mathbb{9}$ 0.0014±0.0003	-	-	dcm.dat = hjd79R310s.dat
Residuals of nine signals (file1 = hjd79R310sResiduals.dat)							
M	Model	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	Fisher-test		
10	model _{1,1,0} $p=4$ $R=0.01530$	5415±124 0.0014±0.0003	-	-	\uparrow $F=8.0$ $Q_F = 0.000029$	\uparrow $F=6.1$ $Q_F = 2.7 \times 10^{-6}$	dcm.dat = hjd1012R110s.dat
11	model _{2,1,0} $p=7$ $R=0.01497$	5094±177 0.02±0.01* \dagger	5122±136 0.02±0.01* \dagger	-	-	\leftarrow $F=4.1$ $Q_F = 0.0062$	dcm.dat = hjd1012R210s.dat
12	model _{3,1,0} $p=10$ $R=0.01480$	5090±120 0.01±0.01* \dagger	5172±119 0.01±0.01* \dagger	127709±319252 0.00±0.05* \dagger	-	-	dcm.dat = hjd1012R310s.dat

Table A9: Long period search between 3000^d and 100000^d. Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴ for HJD-data, otherwise as in Table A7.

Original data (Table A3 = <i>file1</i> = <i>hjdXZAnd.dat</i>)								
M Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,2}	model _{3,1,2}	model _{4,1,2}	
1 model _{1,1,2}	13148±109	-	-	-	↑	↑	↑	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R112s.dat</i>
$p=6$	0.050±0.001	-	-	-	$F=5157$	$F=2907$	$F=2228$	
$R=0.3595$					$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
2 model _{2,1,2}	13420±28	32196 ± 259	-	-	-	↑	↑	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R212s.dat</i>
$p=9$	0.0582±0.0004	0.081±0.001	-	-	-	$F=44.0$	$F=50.9$	
$R=0.02354$					-	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
3 model _{3,1,2}	8124±139	13439±25	32948±340	-	-	-	↑	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R312s.dat</i>
$p=12$	0.0044±0.0004	0.0575±0.0004	0.084±0.001	-	-	-	$F=51.8$	
$R=0.02098$					-	-	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
4 model _{4,1,2}	6346±63	7754±67	13537±28	33507±246	-	-	-	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R412s.dat</i>
$p=15$	0.0055±0.0004	0.0062±0.0004	0.0568±0.0002	0.086±0.001	-	-	-	
$R=0.01834$					-	-	-	
Four signal residuals (<i>file1</i> = <i>hjd14R312sResiduals.dat</i>)								
M Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
5 model _{1,1,0}	4225±17	-	-	-	↑	↑	↑	dcm.dat = <i>hjd58R110s.dat</i>
$p=4$	0.0025±0.0003	-	-	-	$F=25.5$	$F=21.9$	$F=21.3$	
$R=0.01747$					$Q_F = 1.6 \times 10^{-11}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
6 model _{2,1,0}	4393±62	4654±77	-	-	-	↑	↑	dcm.dat = <i>hjd58R210s.dat</i>
• $p=7$	0.01±0.01*†	0.01±0.01*†	-	-	-	$F=17.1$	$F=18.0$	
$R=0.01632$					-	$Q_F = 7.0 \times 10^{-11}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
7 model _{3,1,0}	3714±36	4347 ± 45	4716±66	-	-	-	↑	dcm.dat = <i>hjd58R310s.dat</i>
$p=10$	0.0024±0.0003	0.005±0.005*	0.004±0.005*	-	-	-	$F=18.0$	
$R=0.01558$					-	-	$Q_F = 2.2 \times 10^{-11}$	
8 model _{4,1,0}	3019±27	3732 ± 40	4320±56	4723±100	-	-	-	Figs. 5 and 6
$p=13$	0.0024±0.0002	0.0026±0.0004	0.005±0.003*†	0.004±0.003*†	-	-	-	dcm.dat = <i>hjd58R410s.dat</i>
$R=0.01484$					-	-	-	
Eight signal residuals (<i>file1</i> = <i>hjd58R310sResiduals.dat</i>)								
M Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
9 model _{1,1,0}	5755±444	-	-	-	←	↑	↑	dcm.dat = <i>hjd912R110s.dat</i>
$p=4$	0.0012±0.0003	-	-	-	$F=5.3$	$F=4.5$	$F=3.6$	
$R=0.01465$					$Q_F=0.0013$	$Q_F=0.00014$	$Q_F = 0.00018$	
10 model _{2,1,0}	5695±160	765490±313845	-	-	-	←	←	dcm.dat = <i>hjd912R210s.dat</i>
$p=7$	0.0014±0.0003	0.10±0.06*	-	-	-	$F=3.8$	$F=2.8$	
$R=0.01444$					-	$Q_F=0.010$	$Q_F = 0.011$	
11 model _{3,1,0}	5899±235	7347 ± 341	725806±340851	-	-	-	←	dcm.dat = <i>hjd912R310s.dat</i>
• $p=10$	0.0016±0.0004	0.0011±0.0003	0.08±0.05*†	-	-	-	$F=1.8$	
$R=0.01429$					-	-	$Q_F=0.15$	
12 model _{4,1,0}	5547±393 ⁹	6959 ± 472	6962±2008	725806±356436	-	-	-	
• $p=13$	0.0012±0.0004*†	0.010±0.004*†	0.010±0.005*†	0.09±0.04*†	-	-	-	dcm.dat = <i>hjd912R410s.dat</i>
$R=0.01422$					-	-	-	

Table A10: Long period search between 3000^d and 100000^d. Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³ for D-data, otherwise as in Table A7

Original data (Table A5 \equiv dXZAnd.dat)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,2}	model _{3,1,2}	
1	model _{1,1,2}	13168 \pm 76	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow	
	$p=6$	0.050 \pm 0.002	-	-	$F=4794$	$F=2663$	dcm.dat = d13R112s.dat
	$R=0.3607$				$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
2	model _{2,1,2}	13428 \pm 20	32390 \pm 320	-	-	\uparrow	
	$p=9$	0.0578 \pm 0.0003	0.082 \pm 0.001	-	-	$F=38.1$	dcm.dat = d13R212s.dat
	$R=0.02528$				-	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
3	model _{3,1,2}	8296 \pm 115	13449 \pm 31	33079 \pm 280	-	-	
	$p=12$	0.0043 \pm 0.0004	0.0571 \pm 0.0004	0.084 \pm 0.001	-	-	dcm.dat = d13R312s.dat
	$R=0.02286$				-	-	
Residuals of three signals (d13R312sResiduals.dat)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	
4	model _{1,1,0}	6122 \pm 63	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow	
	$p=4$	0.0039 \pm 0.0003	-	-	$F=14.1$	$F=17.0$	dcm.dat = d46R110s.dat
	$R=0.02078$				$Q_F = 4.9 \times 10^{-9}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
5	model _{2,1,0}	2959 \pm 27	6105 \pm 42	-	-	\uparrow	
	$p=7$	0.0025 \pm 0.0003	0.0040 \pm 0.0003	-	-	$F=19.2$	dcm.dat = d46R210s.dat
	$R=0.02000$				-	$Q_F = 3.9 \times 10^{-12}$	
6	model _{3,1,0}	4432 \pm 55	4585 \pm 69	6129 \pm 66	-	-	
	$p=10$	0.01 \pm 0.02* \dagger	0.01 \pm 0.02* \dagger	0.0044 \pm 0.0003	-	-	dcm.dat = d46R310s.dat
	$R=0.01899$				-	-	
Residuals of six signals (d46R310sResiduals.dat)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	
7	model _{1,1,0}	2972 \pm 30	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow	
	$p=4$	0.0022 \pm 0.0004	-	-	$F=11.0$	$F=8.8$	dcm.dat = d79R110s.dat
	$R=0.01836$				$Q_F = 4.2 \times 10^{-7}$	$Q_F = 2.4 \times 10^{-9}$	
8	model _{2,1,0}	2984 \pm 22	3650 \pm 51	-	-	\uparrow	
	$p=7$	0.0023 \pm 0.0005	0.0020 \pm 0.0004	-	-	$F=6.4$	dcm.dat = d79R210s.dat
	$R=0.01782$				-	$Q_F = 0.00027$	
9	model _{3,1,0}	2990 \pm 28	3651 \pm 40	7523 \pm 38 ^{#9}	-	-	
	$p=10$	0.0023 \pm 0.0002	0.0020 \pm 0.0002	0.0014 \pm 0.0004	-	-	dcm.dat = d79R310s.dat
	$R=0.01751$				-	-	
Residuals of nine signals (d79R310sResiduals.dat)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	
10	model _{1,1,0}	5442 \pm 193	-	-	\leftarrow	\leftarrow	
	$p=4$	0.0013 \pm 0.0003	-	-	$F=3.2$	$F=3.3$	dcm.dat = d1012R110s.dat
	$R=0.01730$				$Q_F = 0.023$	$Q_F = 0.0032$	
11	model _{2,1,0}	5150 \pm 187	5178 \pm 127	-	-	\leftarrow	
	$p=7$	0.02 \pm 0.01* \dagger	0.02 \pm 0.01* \dagger	-	-	$F=3.4$	dcm.dat = d1012R210s.dat
	$R=0.01715$				-	$Q_F = 0.017$	
12	model _{3,1,0}	5151 \pm 222	5179 \pm 185	95518 \pm 29866	-	-	
	$p=10$	0.02 \pm 0.01* \dagger	0.03 \pm 0.02* \dagger	0.00 \pm 0.06*	-	-	dcm.dat = d1012R310s.dat
	$R=0.01699$				-	-	

Table A11: Long period search between 3000^d and 100000^d. Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴ for D-data, otherwise as in Table A7.

Original data (Table A5 = file1 = dXZAnd.dat)								
M Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,2}	model _{3,1,2}	model _{4,1,2}	
1 model _{1,1,2}	13168±86	-	-	-	↑	↑	↑	dcm.dat = d14R112s.dat
$p=6$	0.050±0.002	-	-	-	$F=4794$	$F=2663$	$F=2026$	
$R=0.3607$					$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
2 model _{2,1,2}	13428±28	32390 ± 385	-	-	-	↑	↑	dcm.dat = PRd14R212s.dat
$p=9$	0.0578±0.0006	0.082±0.001	-	-	-	$F=38.1$	$F=46.0$	
$R=0.02528$					-	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
3 model _{3,1,2}	8296±127	13449±22	33079±249	-	-	-	↑	dcm.dat = d14R312s.dat
$p=12$	0.0043±0.0004	0.0571±0.0003	0.084±0.001	-	-	-	$F=48.7$	
$R=0.02286$					-	-	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
4 model _{4,1,2}	6316±79	7956±107	13547±16	33766±282	-	-	-	dcm.dat = d14R412s.dat
$p=15$	0.00533±0.00005	0.0059±0.0004	0.0563±0.0003	0.087±0.001	-	-	-	
$R=0.02013$					-	-	-	
Four signal residuals (file1 = d14R412sResiduals.dat)								
M Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
5 model _{1,1,0}	4266±55	-	-	-	↑	↑	↑	dcm.dat = d58R110s.dat
$p=4$	0.0024±0.0004	-	-	-	$F=21.6$	$F=18.2$	$F=16.5$	
$R=0.01936$					$Q_F = 1.4 \times 10^{-13}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
6 model _{2,1,0}	4431±74	4652 ± 83	-	-	-	↑	↑	dcm.dat = d58R210s.dat
$p=7$	0.006±0.008*†	0.0057±0.008*†	-	-	-	$F=14.0$	$F=13.2$	
$R=0.01827$					-	$Q_F = 6.2 \times 10^{-9}$	$Q_F = 1.7 \times 10^{-14}$	
7 model _{3,1,0}	3710±51	4367 ± 60	4718±88	-	-	-	↑	dcm.dat = d58R310s.dat
$p=10$	0.0023±0.0002	0.005±0.009*†	0.004±0.009*†	-	-	-	$F=12.0$	
$R=0.01759$					-	-	9.1×10^{-8}	
8 model _{4,1,0}	2984±31	3711 ± 33	4355±40	4725±77	-	-	-	dcm.dat = d58R410s.dat
$p=13$	0.0021±0.0004	0.0024±0.0004	0.005±0.001*	0.004±0.001*	-	-	-	
$R=0.01702$					-	-	-	
Eight signal residuals (file1 = d58R410sResiduals.dat)								
M Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
	$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
9 model _{1,1,0}	72581±32214	-	-	-	←	←	↑	dcm.dat = d912R110s.dat
$p=4$	0.07±0.05*†	-	-	-	$F=4.6$	$F=3.7$	$F=3.3$	
$R=0.01684$					$Q_F=0.0034$	$Q_F=0.0011$	0.00057	
10 model _{2,1,0}	6859±227	6910 ± 403	-	-	-	←	←	dcm.dat = d912R210s.dat
$p=7$	0.03±0.02*†	0.03±0.02*†	-	-	-	$F=2.8$	$F=2.6$	
$R=0.01663$					-	$Q_F=0.037$	$Q_F=0.015$	
11 model _{3,1,0}	6756±265	6906 ± 507	726388±309272	-	-	-	←	dcm.dat = d912R310s.dat
$p=10$	0.01±0.01*†	0.01±0.01*†	0.02±0.04*	-	-	-	$F=2.4$	
$R=0.01650$					-	-	$Q_F=0.065$	
12 model _{4,1,0}	5451±386 ⁹	7713 ± 446	7909±272	8046±929	-	-	-	dcm.dat = d912R410s.dat
$p=13$	0.001±0.001*	0.0±0.1*†	0.1±0.2*†	0.08±0.05*†	-	-	-	
$R=0.01639$					-	-	-	

Table A12: Long period search between 3000^d and 100000^d. Test³⁺³⁺³⁺³ for JD-data, otherwise as in Table A7.

Original data (Table A6 \equiv <code>jdXZAnd.dat</code>)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,2}	model _{3,1,2}	
1	model _{1,1,2}	13146 \pm 101	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow	
	$p=6$	0.050 \pm 0.001	-	-	$F=3816$	$F=2111$	<code>dcm.dat = jd13R112s.dat</code>
	$R=0.3605$				$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
2	model _{2,1,2}	13421 \pm 26	31957 \pm 268	-	-	\uparrow	
	$p=9$	0.0585 \pm 0.0004	0.079 \pm 0.001	-	-	$F=36.0$	<code>dcm.dat = jd13R212s.dat</code>
	$R=0.03118$				-	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$	
3	model _{3,1,2}	8011 \pm 126	13438 \pm 32	32705 \pm 426	-	-	
	$p=12$	0.0046 \pm 0.0005	0.0578 \pm 0.0006	0.082 \pm 0.002	-	-	<code>dcm.dat = jd13R312s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02835$				-	-	
Residuals of three signals (<code>jd13R312sResiduals.dat</code>)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	
4	model _{1,1,0}	6032 \pm 60	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow	
	$p=4$	0.0040 \pm 0.0005	-	-	$F=13.5$	$F=14.3$	<code>dcm.dat = jd46R110s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02620$				$Q_F = 1.2 \times 10^{-8}$	$Q_F = 1.0 \times 10^{-15}$	
5	model _{2,1,0}	2954 \pm 22	6021 \pm 55	-	-	\uparrow	
	$p=7$	0.0027 \pm 0.0004	0.0042 \pm 0.0003	-	-	$F=14.6$	<code>dcm.dat = jd46R210s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02526$				-	$Q_F = 2.6 \times 10^{-9}$	
6	model _{3,1,0}	4432 \pm 72	4540 \pm 91	6069 \pm 44	-	-	
	$p=10$	0.01 \pm 0.02* \dagger	0.02 \pm 0.02* \dagger	0.0046 \pm 0.0004	-	-	<code>dcm.dat = jd46R310s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02428$				-	-	
Residuals of six signals (<code>jd46R310sResiduals.dat</code>)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	
7	model _{1,1,0}	2982 \pm 35	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow	
	$p=4$	0.0024 \pm 0.0005	-	-	$F=12.6$	$F=8.7$	<code>dcm.dat = jd79R110s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02351$				$Q_F = 4.3 \times 10^{-8}$	$Q_F = 3.0 \times 10^{-9}$	
8	model _{2,1,0}	2999 \pm 34	3672 \pm 37	-	-	\leftarrow	
	$p=7$	0.0026 \pm 0.0004	0.0024 \pm 0.0004	-	-	$F=4.7$	<code>dcm.dat = jd79R210s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02272$				-	$Q_F=0.003$	
9	model _{3,1,0}	3001 \pm 36	3670 \pm 31	7671 \pm 337 ^{†9}	-	-	
	$p=10$	0.0026 \pm 0.0004	0.0024 \pm 0.0004	0.0014 \pm 0.0004	-	-	<code>dcm.dat = jd79R310s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02243$				-	-	
Residuals of nine signals (<code>jd79R310sResiduals.dat</code>)							
M	Model	Period analysis			Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	
10	model _{1,1,0}	5436 \pm 201	-	-	\leftarrow	\leftarrow	
	$p=4$	0.0013 \pm 0.0003	-	-	$F=2.6$	$F=3.0$	<code>dcm.dat = jd1012R110s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02221$				$Q_F=0.049$	$Q_F=0.0069$	
11	model _{2,1,0}	5446 \pm 374	766660 \pm 274978	-	-	\leftarrow	
	$p=10$	0.0014 \pm 0.0003	0.08 \pm 0.07*	-	-	$F=3.3$	<code>dcm.dat = jd1012R210s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02205$				-	$Q_F=0.020$	
12	model _{3,1,0}	5143 \pm 221	5171 \pm 151	282661 \pm 322887	-	-	
	$p=10$	0.02 \pm 0.02* \dagger	0.02 \pm 0.02* \dagger	0.01 \pm 0.06*	-	-	<code>dcm.dat = jd1012R310s.dat</code>
	$R=0.02185$				-	-	

Table A13: Long period search between 3000^d and 100000^d. Test⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴ for JD-data, otherwise as in Table A7.

		Original data (Table A5 = file1 = jdx2and.dat)				Fisher-test		
M Model	Period analysis				model _{2,1,2}	model _{3,1,2}	model _{4,1,2}	
	P ₁ &A ₁ [d]	P ₂ &A ₂ [d]	P ₃ &A ₃ [d]	P ₄ &A ₄ [d]				
1 model _{1,1,2} p=6 R=0.3605	13146±88 0.050±0.001	-	-	-	F=3816 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	F=2111 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	F=1567 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	dcm.dat = jd14R112s.dat
2 model _{2,1,2} p=9 R=0.03118	13421±20 0.0585±0.0005	31957 ± 297 0.079±0.001	-	-	-	F=36.0 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	F=39.2 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	dcm.dat = jd14R212s.dat
3 model _{3,1,2} p=12 R=0.02835	8011±125 0.0046±0.0004	13438±29 0.0578±0.0005	32705±526 0.082±0.002	-	-	-	F=38.6 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	dcm.dat = jd14R312s.dat
4 model _{4,1,2} p=15 R=0.02560	6283±120 0.005±0.001	7738±186 0.006±0.001	13534±24 0.0572±0.0006	33140±374 0.084±0.001	-	-	-	dcm.dat = jd14R412s.dat
		Four signal residuals (file1 = jd14R412sResiduals.dat)				Fisher-test		
M Model	Period analysis				model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
	P ₁ &A ₁ [d]	P ₂ &A ₂ [d]	P ₃ &A ₃ [d]	P ₄ &A ₄ [d]				
5 model _{1,1,0} p=4 R=0.02482	4186±80 0.0024±0.0005	-	-	-	F=18.1 Q _F =1.9 × 10 ⁻¹¹	F=16.2 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	F=15.6 Q _F <10 ⁻¹⁶	dcm.dat = jd58R110s.dat
6 model _{2,1,0} • p=7 R=0.02364	4430±81 0.01±0.02*†	4584 ± 86 0.01±0.02*†	-	-	-	F=13.8 Q _F =7.8 × 10 ⁻⁹	F=13.8 Q _F =4.0 × 10 ⁻¹⁵	dcm.dat = jd58R210s.dat
7 model _{3,1,0} • p=10 R=0.02277	3692±52 0.0026±0.0004	4354 ± 86 0.01±0.01*†	4695±83 0.00±0.01*†	-	-	-	F=13.3 1.6 × 10 ⁻⁸	dcm.dat = jd58R310s.dat
8 model _{4,1,0} p=13 R=0.02196	3103±37 0.0025±0.0004	3716 ± 28 0.0028±0.0004	4357±70 0.01±0.02*†	4662±96 0.01±0.02*†	-	-	-	dcm.dat = jd58R410s.dat
		Eight signal residuals (file1 = jd58R410sResiduals.dat)				Fisher-test		
M Model	Period analysis				model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
	P ₁ &A ₁ [d]	P ₂ &A ₂ [d]	P ₃ &A ₃ [d]	P ₄ &A ₄ [d]				
9 model _{1,1,0} p=4 R=0.02178	5633±214 0.0012±0.0003	-	-	-	F=3.5 Q _F =0.014	F=2.7 Q _F =0.013	F=2.3 Q _F =0.014	dcm.dat = jd912R110s.dat
10 model _{2,1,0} • p=7 R=0.02157	5629±394 0.0013±0.0004	271462 ± 336800 [†] 0.02±0.09*	-	-	-	F=1.8 Q _F =0.14	F=1.7 Q _F =0.12	dcm.dat = jd912R210s.dat
11 model _{3,1,0} • p=10 R=0.02146	5708±104 0.0014±0.0004	9159 ± 1039 0.0009±0.0003	133667±341095 [†] 0.00±0.09*	-	-	-	F=1.5 Q _F =0.21	dcm.dat = jd912R310s.dat
12 model _{4,1,0} • p=13 R=0.02137	3039±121 0.019±0.008*†	3049 ± 217 0.019±0.008*†	5665±205 ^{¶9} 0.0014±0.0004	168753±298188 0.01±0.06*†	-	-	-	dcm.dat = jd912R410s.dat

Table A14: Comparison of long period search results.

Table A3 HJD-data 1 ^Y signal=No, 1 ^Y window=Yes		Table A5 D-data 1 ^Y signal=No, 1 ^Y window=No		Table A6 JD-data 1 ^Y signal=Yes, 1 ^Y window=Yes	
Table A8: Test ³⁺³⁺³⁺³	Table A9: Test ⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴	Table A10: Test ³⁺³⁺³⁺³	Table A11: Test ⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴	Table A12: Test ³⁺³⁺³⁺³	Table A13: Test ⁴⁺⁴⁺⁴
M	M	M	M	M	M
3 32948 ± 273 0.084 ± 0.001	4 33507 ± 246 0.086 ± 0.001	3 33079 ± 280 0.084 ± 0.001	4 33766 ± 282 0.087 ± 0.001	3 32705 ± 429 0.082 ± 0.002	4 33140 ± 374 0.084 ± 0.001
3 13439 ± 23 0.0575 ± 0.0004	4 13537 ± 28 0.0568 ± 0.0002	3 13449 ± 31 0.0571 ± 0.0004	4 13547 ± 16 0.0563 ± 0.0003	3 13438 ± 32 0.0578 ± 0.0006	4 13534 ± 24 0.0572 ± 0.0006
3 8124 ± 127 0.0044 ± 0.0004	4 7754 ± 67 0.0062 ± 0.0005	3 8296 ± 115 0.0043 ± 0.0004	4 7956 ± 106 0.0059 ± 0.0004	3 8011 ± 126 0.0046 ± 0.0005	4 7738 ± 186 0.006 ± 0.001
6 6092 ± 379 0.0044 ± 0.0004	4 6346 ± 63 0.0055 ± 0.0004	6 6129 ± 66 0.0044 ± 0.0003	4 6316 ± 79 0.00533 ± 0.00005	6 6069 ± 44 0.0046 ± 0.0004	4 6283 ± 120 0.005 ± 0.001
6 4614 ± 80 0.01 ± 0.02*†	8 4723 ± 100 0.004 ± 0.003*†	6 4585 ± 69 0.01 ± 0.02*†	8 4725 ± 77 0.004 ± 0.001*	6 4540 ± 91 0.02 ± 0.02*†	8 4662 ± 96 0.01 ± 0.02*†
6 4480 ± 91 0.01 ± 0.02*†	8 4320 ± 56 0.005 ± 0.003*†	6 4432 ± 55 0.01 ± 0.02*†	8 4355 ± 40 0.005 ± 0.001*	6 4432 ± 72 0.01 ± 0.02*†	8 4357 ± 70 0.01 ± 0.02*†
9 7518 ± 219 ^{¶9} 0.0014 ± 0.0003	8 3732 ± 40 0.0026 ± 0.0004	9 7523 ± 38 0.0014 ± 0.0004 ^{¶9}	8 3711 ± 33 0.0024 ± 0.0004	9 7671 ± 337 0.0014 ± 0.0004 ^{¶9}	8 3716 ± 28 0.0028 ± 0.0004
9 3687 ± 34 0.0022 ± 0.0003	8 3019 ± 27 0.0024 ± 0.0002	9 3651 ± 40 0.0020 ± 0.0002	8 2984 ± 31 0.0021 ± 0.0004	9 3670 ± 31 0.0024 ± 0.0004	8 3103 ± 37 0.0025 ± 0.0004
9 3006 ± 18 0.0026 ± 0.0004	12 725806 ± 356436 0.06 ± 0.09*†	9 2990 ± 28 0.0023 ± 0.0002	12 8046 ± 929 0.08 ± 0.05*†	9 3001 ± 36 0.0026 ± 0.0004	12 168753 ± 298188 0.01 ± 0.06*†
12 127709 ± 319252 0.00 ± 0.05*†	12 6962 ± 2008 0.010 ± 0.005*†	12 95518 ± 29866 0.00 ± 0.06*†	12 7909 ± 272 0.1 ± 0.2*†	12 282661 ± 322887 0.01 ± 0.06*	12 5665 ± 205 ^{¶9} 0.0014 ± 0.0004
12 5172 ± 119 0.01 ± 0.01*†	12 6959 ± 472 0.010 ± 0.004*†	12 5179 ± 185 0.03 ± 0.02*†	12 7713 ± 446 0.0 ± 0.1*†	12 5171 ± 151 0.02 ± 0.02*†	12 3049 ± 217 0.019 ± 0.008*†
12 5090 ± 120 0.01 ± 0.01*†	12 5547 ± 392 ^{¶9} 0.0012 ± 0.0004*†	12 5151 ± 222 0.02 ± 0.01*†	12 5451 ± 386 ^{¶9} 0.001 ± 0.001*	12 5143 ± 221 0.02 ± 0.02*†	12 3039 ± 121 0.019 ± 0.008*†

Table A15: Short period search between 300^d and 3000^d. Fours best periods for the eight signal residuals (HJD-data: M=1-4, D-data: M=5-8, JD-data: M=9-12), otherwise as in Table A7.

HJD-data									
Eight signal residuals (<i>file1</i> = <i>hjd58R410sResiduals.dat</i>)									
M	Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
1	model _{1,1,0}	616.4 ± 11	-	-	-	←	↑	↑	
	$p = 4$	0.0013 ± 0.0002	-	-	-	$F = 4.8$	$F = 4.2$	$F = 5.2$	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R1101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01462$					$Q_F = 0.0026$	$Q_F = 0.00038$	$Q_F = 5.6 \times 10^{-7}$	
2	model _{2,1,0}	365.5 ± 10	616.6 ± 14	-	-	-	←	↑	
	$p = 7$	0.0018 ± 0.0005	0.0013 ± 0.0004	-	-	-	$F = 3.5$	$F = 5.4$	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R2101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01443$					-	$Q_F = 0.014$	$Q_F = 1.6 \times 10^{-5}$	
3	model _{3,1,0}	314.4 ± 13	365.4 ± 8	617.2 ± 1.9	-	-	-	↑	
	$p = 10$	0.0010 ± 0.0002	0.0018 ± 0.0005	0.0013 ± 0.0002	-	-	-	$F = 7.2$	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R3101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01429$				-	-	-	$Q_F = 8.8 \times 10^{-5}$	
4	model _{4,1,0}	365.6 ± 9.5	451.8 ± 19	591.6 ± 187	616.8 ± 21	-	-	-	
	$p = 13$	0.0018 ± 0.0004	0.0012 ± 0.0003	0.0012 ± 0.0003* [†]	0.0012 ± 0.0003* [†]	-	-	-	dcm.dat = <i>hjd14R4101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01401$					-	-	-	
D-data									
Eight signal residuals (<i>file1</i> = <i>d58R410sResiduals.dat</i>)									
M	Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
5	model _{1,1,0}	364.9 ± 0.3	-	-	-	←	↑	↑	
	$p = 4$	0.0022 ± 0.0003	-	-	-	$F = 5.2$	$F = 6.4$	$F = 5.4$	dcm.dat = <i>d14R1101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01635$					$Q_F = 0.0015$	$Q_F = 1.2 \times 10^{-6}$	$Q_F = 3.3 \times 10^{-7}$	
6	model _{2,1,0}	364.9 ± 0.3	593.3 ± 20	-	-	-	↑	↑	
	$p = 7$	0.0022 ± 0.0003	0.0013 ± 0.0002	-	-	-	$F = 7.5$	$F = 5.4$	dcm.dat = <i>d14R2101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01612$					-	$Q_F = 5.4 \times 10^{-5}$	$Q_F = 1.5 \times 10^{-5}$	
7	model _{3,1,0}	364.9 ± 34	593.1 ± 26	2244 ± 49	-	-	-	←	
	$p = 10$	0.0023 ± 0.0004	0.0013 ± 0.0003	0.0016 ± 0.0003	-	-	-	$F = 3.2$	dcm.dat = <i>d14R3101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01579$				-	-	-	$Q_F = 0.022$	
8	model _{4,1,0}	364.9 ± 22	593.1 ± 30	2244 ± 372	7714 ± 1367	-	-	-	
	$p = 13$	0.0023 ± 0.0003	0.0012 ± 0.0003	0.0016 ± 0.0004* [†]	0.0010 ± 0.0002* [†]	-	-	-	dcm.dat = <i>d14R3101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01565$					-	-	-	
JD-data									
Eight signal residuals (<i>file1</i> = <i>jd58R410sResiduals.dat</i>)									
M	Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test			
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model _{2,1,0}	model _{3,1,0}	model _{4,1,0}	
9	model _{1,1,0}	365.34 ± 0.08	-	-	-	←	←	↑	Fig. 9
	$p = 4$	0.0110 ± 0.0004	-	-	-	$F = 2.2$	$F = 3.7$	$F = 4.3$	dcm.dat = <i>jd14R1101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01483$					$Q_F = 0.085$	$Q_F = 0.0011$	$Q_F = 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$	
10	model _{2,1,0}	362.6 ± 1.1	365.4 ± 0.6	-	-	-	←	↑	
	$p = 7$	0.001 ± 0.002* [†]	0.010 ± 0.003* [†]	-	-	-	$F = 5.2$	$F = 5.4$	dcm.dat = <i>jd14R2101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01474$					-	$Q_F = 0.0014$	$Q_F = 1.6 \times 10^{-5}$	
11	model _{3,1,0}	362.6 ± 1.3	365.4 ± 30	595.3 ± 23	-	-	-	↑	
	$p = 10$	0.001 ± 0.002* [†]	0.010 ± 0.001* [†]	0.0012 ± 0.0004	-	-	-	$F = 5.5$	dcm.dat = <i>jd14R3101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01453$				-	-	-	$Q_F = 0.00090$	
12	model _{4,1,0}	362.8 ± 1.0	365.5 ± 38	595.7 ± 26	5462 ± 848	-	-	-	
	$p = 13$	0.001 ± 0.002* [†]	0.010 ± 0.002* [†]	0.0012 ± 0.0002	0.0013 ± 0.0002	-	-	-	dcm.dat = <i>jd14R4101.dat</i>
	$R = 0.01431$					-	-	-	

Table A16: M_1 and M_2 coefficients of $p(t)$.

Model	M_1	M_2
Table A9: M=1	-0.930 ± 0.007	0.209 ± 0.003
Table A9: M=2	-0.646 ± 0.006	0.089 ± 0.002
Table A9: M=3	-0.635 ± 0.006	0.085 ± 0.002
Table A9: M=4	-0.627 ± 0.005	0.082 ± 0.002